

**SOLUTIONS TO ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS ASSOCIATED
WITH WATER SCARCITY**

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Summary: In the article, prevention of water shortage is done through effective use of natural resources. Available material natural resources are divided into non-renewable and renewable resources. In addition, there are intangible resources, which have their place in the development of society, but due to the importance of material resources and their importance for human consumption, the existence of their reserves, the fact that all types of natural resources are not unlimited, dividing natural resources into non-renewable and renewable resources, and the requirements for its reserves, and how to use them for the sustainable development of society.

Keywords: water resources, underground and surface water, water basins, efficient use of water.

The development of society is carried out through the consumption and use of natural resources. When we say consumer, we should understand not only humanity, but the whole world of living creatures and plants. We divide existing material natural resources into non-renewable and renewable resources. In addition, there are intangible resources, which have their place in the development of society, but due to the importance of material resources and their importance for human consumption, we will focus on their reserves and the conditions of their use.

All types of natural resources are not unlimited, their importance is felt even more as the demand increases. So, we will divide natural resources into non-renewable and

renewable resources, discuss the requirements for their reserves, and how to use them for the sustainable development of society.

As we know, water resources are renewable resources and their quantity and reserves are not evenly distributed in all places. Water is scarce in many parts of the world, and it varies from place to place depending on the pace of development and the level of community development. Below we will discuss the role of water resources in sustainable development and the principles of its management and effective use.

It is known that water resources are divided into underground and surface water. The balance between all water reserves and the demand for them is already disturbed, but this imbalance can be said to be different in different regions of the earth. If the root causes of this problem are analyzed, it will be possible to prevent it in other regions and eliminate it in the initial stages. Therefore, the main reasons that cause environmental problems related to water shortage are:

- The geographical location of the territory and the fact that natural resources do not meet consumer demand, that is, the balance of consumer demand: resource quantity ratio is inherently disturbed;

- Use of water resources, non-availability of cadastre of their consumption and their unaccounted/unreasonable use;

- Unreasonable use of drinking water for other industrial and agricultural purposes, as well as the impossibility of replenishing water reserves with payments for this;

- Man-made pollution of existing water bodies and limitation of their future use.

Each of these causes has several small and perfect factors, which are studied separately in many disciplines.

What measures should be taken if there is a shortage of water resources in places due to the reasons listed above? The solution to this problem is achieved by finding an answer to the question. They will consist of:

- The root causes of the problem are studied and they are solved through their analysis;

- In areas with water shortages, water use is strictly controlled and only in justified cases and on the basis of certain conditions (payments, quantities and non-pollution conditions) are allowed to use it;

- When the demand of consumers is studied, their requirements are studied by category, only in justified cases they are allowed to use water, in other cases restrictions are placed on water use;

- The most important thing is that based on the analysis of the causes of water shortage, measures to improve the situation will be developed, and the task of implementing it will be assigned to specific official organizations, the implementation will be under strict control, and the regional commissions will submit their reports in due time.

Now that water resources are sufficient, what should be done in areas where there is no water shortage? - question is no less important than the first one. If its measures are developed, it is inevitable that water problems will arise in this area in the near future. Sometimes such areas go beyond the borders of one country and cover the territories of several countries. In that case, the issue will be controlled by regional basin organizations as a transboundary issue and will be under the control of international organizations. It is recommended to carry out the following activities in the areas of this category:

- Despite the fact that there is enough water, to use its reserves sparingly and rationally;

- The demand for water resources, that is, a perspective forecast of consumption in the near future is developed;

- Measures to protect existing water sources from pollution, drying up and loss of capacity will be developed and implemented;

- Based on forecasts, measures to prevent environmental problems such as water shortages and pollution that may occur in the future will be developed and implemented.

In both cases, the intensity of the development of the society, its uniqueness and the requirements of the time should be taken into account. Therefore, it is necessary to follow the principles of sustainable development in order to supply water for use as a natural resource for future generations and consumers. If the use of water is managed sustainably, that is, if it is implemented based on all principles, its shortage can be prevented or eliminated.

So, through sustainable management of water resources, problems can be prevented, and existing ones can be eliminated. For this, it is recommended to take the following measures:

- Maintaining a stable balance between the available water resource and its demand/demand;
- Use of modern technologies in the water supply system;
- Limitation of unproductive use of water through financial leverage;
- Application of water reuse and sequential use technologies;
- Implementation of transboundary waters cadastre;
- Ensuring the effectiveness of capital funds spent on the water supply system;
- Extending the productivity and stable operation period of buildings;
- Reducing and controlling water consumption through efficient use;
- Giving the next generation the right and opportunity to fully use and consume water;
- To realize that all living beings benefit from natural waters;
- Adherence to ecological ethics and moral standards;
- Training of personnel who meet the modern requirements of wide-profile water supply and efficient use of water;
- Raising public awareness of current and future environmental problems related to water.

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